

OnSSET-Based Electrification Planning for Remote Communities in Northern Ghana

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study applies the OnSSET modeling framework to evaluate least-cost electrification pathways for Ghana's Northern cluster by 2030. Two scenarios are assessed: a Business-as-Usual (BAU) case centered on grid expansion and a Decentralized scenario prioritizing off-grid solutions such as Solar Home Systems (SHS) and mini-grids. Both scenarios achieve universal access for over 4.37 million people; however, the Decentralized approach delivers a cost saving of 18% (USD 626.78 million vs. USD 767.27 million) while increasing total installed capacity. The results show that grid extension is economically viable only in high-density or industrial areas, whereas off-grid technologies offer more suitable solutions for rural and sparsely populated settlements. These findings align with Ghana's National Energy Transition Framework and Renewable Energy Master Plan, reinforcing the need to scale up decentralized electrification through targeted policies, financing mechanisms, and local capacity development.

1. Introduction

Access to electricity is widely recognized as a key enabler of economic growth, social development, and poverty alleviation. In Ghana, national efforts such as the National Electrification Scheme (NES), the Self-Help Electrification Programme (SHEP), and the Ghana Energy Development and Access Project (GEDAP) have driven notable progress over the past three decades (IEA, 2013; Ministry of Energy, 2010). As of 2024, national electricity access stood at 89.03%, with urban areas approaching full coverage. The Northern cluster, comprising Savannah, North East, Upper West, and Upper East regions however, lags behind with an average access rate of 73.2%, leaving over one million people unelectrified (Energy Commission, 2025). The cluster presents unique challenges to traditional electrification approaches. Settlements are often small, dispersed, and situated in geographically challenging terrain with limited infrastructure, making grid extension logistically difficult and economically burdensome (Kemausuor & Ackom, 2017). The combination of low population density, long distances from the existing grid, and institutional and financial constraints has contributed to persistent access gaps. In light of these challenges, off-grid technologies such as SHS and mini-grids are gaining attention as cost-effective alternatives.

The purpose of this study is to support evidence-based electrification planning by evaluating technology options and cost-effective pathways to achieve universal electricity access in Ghana's underserved Northern cluster. Specifically, the study aims to identify spatially optimal electrification technologies for each settlement in the target region and estimate the total investment needed for implementation.

2. Methodology

This study applies a spatially explicit modeling approach using the Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET) to identify the least-cost electrification options for Ghana's Northern cluster over the period 2024–2030. OnSSET simulates electrification outcomes by combining geospatial population data, infrastructure layers, and techno-economic parameters to determine the most cost-effective technology, grid extension, mini-grid, or standalone system, for each settlement (Korkovelos et al., 2019). The scope of the analysis covers the four administrative regions within the Northern cluster: Savannah,

Upper West, Upper East, and North East. These regions were selected due to their comparatively low electrification rates as shown in figure 1. The data inputs included population distribution (WorldPop 2020), projected population growth to 2030, urban/rural household sizes, electricity demand tiers (based on ESMAP's Multi-Tier Framework), location of existing MV grid infrastructure, and technology cost parameters sourced from national reports and international benchmarks.

ELECTRICITY ACCESS MAPS OF GHANA

Figure 1: National population electricity access rate

2.1 Scenarios

- The Business-as-usual scenario (BAU) represents a trajectory where Ghana continues its current electrification efforts without any major policy or financial interventions beyond those already in place. Grid expansion remains the primary approach under the SHEP, which targets communities within 20 km of existing 11/33 kV grid lines (Ministry of Energy, 2010). Costs of technologies reflect current market averages, with no additional reductions beyond general global trends.
- The Decentralized scenario prioritizes off-grid technologies such as solar mini-grids, hydro mini-grids, and SHS, as the most suitable solutions for electrifying low-density and remote communities. Guided by the Scaling-Up Renewable Energy Programme (SREP) to Electrify Off-Grid Communities (Ministry of Energy, 2025), this approach relies on donor funding, tax incentive, government subsidies, and market stimulation to drive down costs. Grid extension is reserved for densely populated and industrial zones, where its deployment is more economically viable. Grid extension is reserved for dense and industrial zones.

2.2 Assumptions

Electricity demand is estimated using the ESMAP Multi-Tier Framework, assigning rural households to Tier 3 and urban households to Tier 5. In the decentralised scenario, cost reductions of 30% for solar home systems (SHS) and 25% for mini-grids are applied, based on assumptions from the Scaling-up Renewable Energy Program (SREP). Under the business-as-usual scenario, a 20 km buffer distance is used for automatic grid intensification, with a maximum allowable cost of \$2,000 per household for forced grid connections

3. Results

The model evaluated electrification outcomes for the Northern cluster under two scenarios, Business-as-usual and Decentralized, covering population electrified, new connections, additional capacity, investment costs, and emissions.

3.1 BAU Scenario

In the BAU scenario, the electrification plan achieves full coverage of the projected 2030 population in the Northern cluster, connecting a total of 4,378,013 people. The scenario relies heavily on grid-based solutions, with grid densification and grid extension jointly serving approximately 91.6% of the population, 2.82 million (64.4%) through densification and 1.18 million (27.2%) via grid extension. Off-grid technologies play a minor role, with SHS systems covering 321,882 people (7.4%) and PV Hybrid mini-grids reaching 53,277 people (1.2%). In terms of capacity expansion, the BAU scenario delivers a total additional installed capacity of 114.87 MW. This includes 49.1 MW from densification, 49.75 MW from grid extension, 8.85 MW from SHS, and 7.17 MW from PV mini-grids. Notably, wind and hydro mini-grids are not deployed in this scenario, indicating a limited diversification of off-grid generation sources. A total of 23 PV Hybrid mini-grids are added under this scenario. These outcomes reflect a continuation of Ghana's current grid-led policies, where the Self-Help Electrification Programme (SHEP) supports expansion within 20 km of existing transmission lines. As shown in Figure 1, grid-based technologies dominate coverage in the business-as-usual scenario, particularly through densification and extension.

Figure 1: Least-cost Technology split in 2030 under BAU scenario

Figure 2: Impact Metrics by Technology in the Business-as-Usual (BAU) Scenario

3.2 Decentralised scenario

In the Decentralized scenario, the same 4.38 million people are connected, but with a major pivot toward off-grid solutions. Grid densification continues to serve 2.82 million people (64.4%), while grid extension drops to just 440,827 people (10.1%). Off-grid technologies expand substantially: SHS systems reach 587,064 people (13.4%), PV hybrid mini-grids connect 521,644 people (11.9%), and hydro mini-grids, though modest, serve 3,554 people (0.08%). Altogether, off-grid solutions account for 25.4% of the population, more than triple their share under the BAU pathway. The total additional

installed capacity increases to 122.57 MW, up from 114.87 MW in BAU. This includes 16.11 MW from SHS, 27.58 MW from PV hybrid mini-grids, and a small but relevant 0.11 MW from hydro mini-grids. A total of 332 PV Hybrid mini-grids and 3 hydro mini-grids are added under this scenario. This shift reflects a decentralized electrification approach, enabled by policies such as the Scaling-Up Renewable Energy Program (SREP), which incentivize solar and hydro adoption through subsidies, PAYG models, and local assembly support, particularly in remote and sparsely populated regions

Figure 3: Least-cost Technology split in 2030 under Decentralized scenario

Figure 4: Impact Metrics by Technology in the Decentralized scenario

3.3 Total investment

In terms of total investment, the Decentralized scenario requires 626.78 million USD, representing an 18.3% reduction compared to the 767.27 million USD projected under the BAU scenario. This decline is primarily due to the sharp decrease in grid extension investment, from 477.7 million USD in BAU to 197.77 million USD in the decentralized case. While off-grid technologies such as SHS and hybrid mini-grids see increased financial allocations (rising to 180.47 million USD and 116.34 million USD, respectively), they still offer a more cost-effective solution per connection in remote, low-demand areas.

The decentralized model demonstrates how strategic investment in off-grid systems can significantly lower overall costs while maintaining universal access targets.

Figure 5: Total Investment by Technology under BAU and Decentralized Scenarios

4. Discussion

The modelling results support the shift toward decentralized energy solutions in Ghana’s Northern cluster, aligning with the objectives outlined in the country’s major energy policy frameworks. These include the Renewable Energy Master Plan (REMP), the (IPSMP), the National Energy Transition Framework (NETF), and the Ghana Energy Transition and Investment Plan (GETIP), all of which emphasize the need to diversify energy access strategies using context-appropriate technologies to ensure universal access, especially in underserved areas (Ghana Renewable Energy Master Plan, 2019; Integrated Power System Master Plan for Ghana, 2018; Ministry of Energy, 2021). The Decentralised scenario modeled in this study mirrors many of these national priorities, particularly the REMP’s focus on off-grid technologies such as mini-grids and Solar Home Systems (SHS), the IPSMP’s prioritization of least-cost approaches for sparsely populated

communities, and the NETF and GETIP's emphasis on equitable, low-carbon, and inclusive energy access. The results, highlighting a 60% reduction in investment cost when transitioning from grid extension to decentralized options, as well as expanded energy access through SHS and mini-grids, affirm the technical and financial feasibility of these policy ambitions. However, increased emissions from PV-diesel hybrid systems suggest a gap in current policy direction that could be addressed by prioritizing cleaner battery-supported mini-grid technologies and diversifying with micro-hydro and wind where viable.

These findings are supported by a growing body of academic and policy research. (Korkovelos et al., 2019) demonstrated that spatially explicit least-cost modelling in Malawi favours off-grid systems in low-density settings. Kemausuor et al. (2014) reached similar conclusions in Ghana using the Network Planner tool, showing that standalone systems and mini-grids offer the most viable solutions for northern and remote communities. The World Bank's Global Electrification Platform (GEP) also advocates a decentralization-focused pathway in areas with challenging grid economics. A study by Mentis et al. (2017), using the OnSSET modelling framework, further confirmed that for regions like West Africa, decentralized PV systems often offer the lowest levelized cost of electricity in rural zones. The alignment between these findings and the outcomes of this study strengthens the policy relevance of promoting solar-based off-grid electrification for remote areas in Ghana.

The implications are clear, if Ghana is to meet its 100% access target by 2030 and align with net-zero emission ambitions, a balanced strategy that scales up clean decentralized technologies while phasing out diesel-based generation is essential. There is potential for policies under GETIP and NETF to further emphasize clean energy mini-grids by tightening emission standards and subsidizing storage integration.

Insights and Policy Recommendations:

- Decentralized systems (SHS and mini-grids) are not only cost-effective but also the fastest route to universal access in dispersed settlements. These should be prioritized in implementation of GETIP and REMP.

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- Emission reductions can be enhanced through policy support for hybrid systems that rely less on fossil fuels. This includes incentives for lithium-ion battery storage and clean energy micro-grids.
 - Local assembly of SHS components, as envisioned under REMP, can drive down costs further and create green jobs.
 - Results-based financing and PAYG models should be scaled up to increase SHS adoption among low-income households.

4.1 Limitations of the Study

While the model incorporates spatial, demographic, and technical data, several limitations affect precision. Technology cost data may not reflect rapid market changes. Emission estimates do not account for seasonal load variation or improvements in diesel efficiency. Social acceptance, financing availability, and institutional readiness were also not factored into the cost and feasibility assessments.

4.2 Areas for Future Research

Future studies should incorporate dynamic demand modeling that includes productive use and economic activities. There is also need for cost-benefit analyses comparing battery-supported mini-grids with other cleaner alternatives like solar-wind hybrids or micro-hydro where geographically viable.

5. Conclusion

This study set out to determine the least-cost and most suitable electrification strategy for Ghana's Northern cluster, with the goal of achieving universal access by 2030. The modelling results clearly show that decentralized energy solutions, particularly standalone solar home systems, hydro and PV-based mini-grids, offer a more cost-effective and scalable path compared to traditional grid extension. With a potential investment reduction of over 18% and increased capacity and reach, decentralized options align strongly with Ghana's energy policy priorities.

Key lessons include the efficiency of tailoring electrification strategies to settlement density and the importance of integrating cleaner technology choices to meet both energy and climate goals. Moving forward, Ghana should prioritize clean mini-grids and SHS in its national electrification strategy, supported by subsidies, innovative financing models like PAYG, and targeted policies that reduce technology costs. Policymakers should also consider phasing out diesel in hybrid systems and investing in alternatives like battery storage and micro-hydro where feasible. Ensuring community involvement, enhancing local technical capacity, and integrating productive use planning will be essential for sustaining long-term energy access in remote regions.

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